

Design of a hyperspectral imaging goniometer for appearance characterization: supplement

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**DESIGN OF A SNAPSHOT HYPERSPECTRAL GONIORADIOMETER FOR
APPEARANCE CHARACTERIZATION: SUPPLEMENTAL DOCUMENT**

Fig. S1. Obtained spectra for the HSI goniometer compared to conventional measurements from a portable spectrophotometer. Solid black lines indicate measurements from the Xrite MA T6, black dashed lines show the measurements from the HSI goniometer setup. Gray dashed lines show the ratio between the Xrite Ma T6 measurements and the HSI goniometer setup measurements. Dark blue dashed lines show the measurements from the halogen setup, while light blue dashed lines show the ratio between the Xrite MA T6 and halogen setup measurements.